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The Grammatical Profile of Arabic Poetry

Abstract

This article is devoted to the analysis of selected couplets from Ibn Manzur's "Lisan al-Arab" - The Language of the Arabs. Most of these couplets are concerned with the essentialisation and modification of certain prefixes used in Arabic speech, i.e. one prefix expressing the meaning of another prefix. The article aims to shed light on the role of Arabic poetry in the medieval scientific environment and to identify the place of Arabic poetry in the solution of linguistic problems. Arabic literature begins with the interpretation of Arabic poetry. The presentation of linguistic problems with reference to the pearls of Arabic poetry is an indication of the great role of Arabic poetry, i.e. Arabic literature, in illuminating linguistic problems. The linguistic analysis of Arabic poetry is often one of the factors that facilitate its philological analysis. This analysis can serve as a fundamental tool for fully understanding the content of Arabic poetry, approaching the poet's means of artistic expression, and understanding the poet's imagination. The study of Arabic poetry, its study based on medieval sources, the consideration of the unique style of expression of the Holy Qur'an in this study, and the resulting parallel comparison leads to a more accurate understanding of both Arabic poetry, Islamic law and linguistics, and the discovery of many topics unknown to us. Such studies have a special importance in terms of the presentation of interdisciplinary interaction.

Keywords: *Ibn Manzūr, Lisān al-‘arab, ‘Alqama al-Faḥl, Zuhayr bin Abī Sulmā, Arabic Grammar, Shāhid Bayt*

Arap Şiirinin Dilbilgisi Profili

Öz

Bu makale, İbn Manzur'un "Lisanü'l-Arab" - Arapların Dili adlı eserinden seçilmiş beyitlerin incelenmesine ayrılmıştır. Bu beyitlerin çoğu, Arapça konuşmada kullanılan bazı öneklerin özleştirilmesi ve değiştirilmesiyle, yani bir önekin başka bir önekin anlamını ifade etmesiyle ilgilidir. Makale, Arap şiirinin ortaçağ bilimsel ortamında oynadığı role ışık tutmayı ve dilbilimle ilgili sorunların çözümünde Arap şiirinin yerini belirlemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Arap edebiyatı, Arap şiirinin yorumlanmasıyla başlar. Dilbilimsel sorunların Arap şiirinin incileri referans alınarak sunulması, Arap şiirinin, yani Arap edebiyatının dilbilimsel sorunları aydınlatmadaki büyük rolünün bir göstergesidir. Arap şiirinin dilbilimsel analizi, genellikle filolojik analizini kolaylaştıran faktörlerden biridir. Bu analiz, Arap şiirinin içeriğini tam olarak anlamak, şairin sanatsal ifade araçlarına yaklaşmak ve şairin hayallerini anlamak için temel bir araç görevi görebilir. Arap şiirinin incelenmesi, ortaçağ kaynaklarına dayalı olarak incelenmesi, Kur'an-ı Kerim'in kendine özgü ifade tarzının bu çalışmada ele alınması ve sonuç olarak ortaya çıkan paralel karşılaştırma, hem Arap şiirinin, hem İslam hukukunun hem de dilbiliminin daha doğru anlaşılmasına ve bizim için bilinmeyen birçok konunun keşfedilmesine yol açmaktadır. Bu tür çalışmalar, disiplinler arası etkileşimin sunumu açısından da özel bir öneme sahiptir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İbn Manzur, Lisan-ı Arab, Alkemetü'l-Fahl, Züheyr bin Ebî Sülmâ, Arap nahvi, Şehîd Beyt

Introduction

The article is devoted to the analysis of several shâhid bayts – verses cited in Ibn Manzûr's work Lisân al-arab (The Language of the Arabs). It should be noted that Lisân al-arab was written in the late 13th century. Considering the historical context of that period, the reason why the work was specifically titled The Language of the Arabs also becomes clear. It is well known that by the end of the 13th century, the Arab Caliphate had completely disappeared from the political scene, and smaller states had emerged in the territories once ruled by the great Arab Caliphate. This political fragmentation called into question not only the status of the Arabic literary language, but also Arabic literature as a whole, its historical legacy, cultural heritage, and, in short, the future of the Arab world. It was precisely for this reason that Ibn Manzûr authored his fifteen-volume work Lisân al-arab, leaving behind an encyclopedic source that encompasses numerous fields of Arabic philology for future generations. Thanks to this monumental work, tens of thousands of verses belonging to Arabic poetry have been preserved and transmitted to our time. Each of these verses pierces the heart of history, traversing centuries to provide us with abundant insights into the Arab literary imagination. The article analyzes

eleven selected verses from the aforementioned work by Ibn Manzūr, offering their literary and linguistic interpretation.

1. Poetic Examples Involving Majrūrāt and Their Relation to the Genitive Case

Majrūrāt refers to the category in Arabic grammar mainly associated with nouns and nominal groups that are governed in the genitive case. When a nominal phrase follows certain prepositions, functions as the second term in an idāfa (construct phrase), or is possessed, it takes the genitive case. The most typical prepositions include *min*, *ilā*, ‘*an*, ‘*alā*, *fī*, *bi*, *li*, *kāf*, *wāw-l-qasm*, *tā’ al-qasm*, *mud*, *mundu*, *raubba*, *hattā*, *halā*, ‘*adā*, *ḥāšā*. One distinctive feature of prepositions is their potential interchangeability – one may substitute another in usage. In *Lisān al-‘Arab*, Ibn Manzūr cites numerous poetic examples related to majrūrāt and possessive constructions. This study aims to analyze a selection of poetic examples by interpreting the grammatical markers present in the verses.

In his *Asrār al-‘Arabiyya*, al-Anbārī divides prepositions into two categories: 1) those used exclusively as prepositions (*mā yalzam al-jarr*), such as *min*, *ilā*, *fī*, *li*, *bi*, *raubba*; 2) those that acquire substantive meaning and do not always govern genitive (*mā lā yalzam al-jarr*), including ‘*an*, ‘*alā*, *kāf*, *ḥāšā*, *halā*, *muz*, and *mundu* (Abū al-Barakāt al-Anbārī, 1957). In the following couplet cited by Ibn Manzur, we observe that the preposition "‘an" is used in the sense of direction, side, or region; in other words, it becomes nominalized and gains a specific meaning. The author explains that since the Arabs use the expression "min ‘anhu" (meaning *from his direction*), the particle "‘an" can function both as a preposition and as a noun. One of the factors proving that "‘anhu" acts as a noun in this case is the fact that it is preceded by another preposition, "min" This is because a preposition cannot precede another preposition of the same type; it can only come before a noun or a noun phrase

فَقُلْتُ لِلرَّكْبِ لَمَّا أَنْ عَلَا بِهِمْ مِنْ عَنِ الْيَمِينِ الْحَيَّيَا نَظْرَةً قَبْلُ

(Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 9, p. 441).

Translation: “When I said to the riders, as they ascended, ‘Look ahead from the side of Hubayya”.

The shāhid is "an" wick used here as a noun meaning "side" or "party." The verse belongs to al-Qutami, the nephew of the Umayyad poet al-Akhtal. His real name was ‘Umayr ibn Shuwaym. The verse cited by Ibn Manzur is found in the poet's Diwan (*Dīwān al-Qutāmī*, 2001: 198). This particular verse is the 27th couplet of a 42-verse panegyric composed by al-Qutami in praise of ‘Abd al-Wāḥid ibn al-Ḥārīṭ ibn al-Ḥakam ibn Abī al-‘Āṣ ibn Umayya.

Another couplet demonstrates *an* used in the sense of *ba‘da* (after):

وَتُضْجِي فَتَيْبُ الْمِسْكِ فَوْقَ فِرَاشِهَا نُؤُومُ الضُّحَى لَمْ تَنْتَطِقْ عَنْ تَفَضُّلِ

(Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 9, p. 442).

Translation: “ (She is) surrounded by musk particles on her bed; she spends the mornings sleeping, having uttered nothing ‘after the light garments’”

Here *an tafaddul(i)* is understood as *ba ‘da tafaddul(i)*; *tafaddul* signifies light night attire. The poet describes the beloved resting in luxury. The couplet is attributed to Imru’ al-Qays (Diwan Imru’ al-Qays, 1984, p. 17).

Ibn Manzūr provides valuable information regarding the preposition "bi-" (بِ), noting that it can also be used in the sense of "an" (عَنْ). To support his argument, he first refers to the Qur’ān, citing the verse فَسْئَلْ بِهِ خَيْرًا – *ask one well-informed about it* (al-Furqān, 25:59). He interprets this verse as أَي سَلْ عَنْهُ خَيْرًا يَخْبِرُكَ – *that is, ask someone knowledgeable about it so that he may inform you*. In other words, in this verse, the preposition "bi-" (بِ) is used in the meaning of "an" (عَنْ). The author then further supports his point by citing the following line of poetry:

فَإِنْ تَسْأَلُونِي بِالنِّسَاءِ، فَإِنِّي بَصِيرٌ بِأَدْوَاءِ النِّسَاءِ طَيِّبٌ

(Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 1, p. 298).

Translation: If you ask me about women, (know that) I am fully aware of all their shortcomings, negative traits, and afflictions; I see and know them intimately.

Commenting on the verse, Ibn Manzūr states that in the phrase *بالنساء*, the preposition "bi-" (بِ) is used in the meaning of "an" (عَنْ), interpreting it as أَي تَسْأَلُونِي عَنِ النِّسَاءِ – *that is, you ask me about women*. The cited line of poetry belongs to the pre-Islamic poet Alqama al-Faḥl (d. 603) (Aḥmad Ṣaqr, 1935, p. 11). After citing the poetic evidence, Ibn Manzūr further supports his position with another Qur’ānic verse. He refers to Sūrat al-Infīṭār, verse 6: مَا غَرَّكَ بِرَبِّكَ الْكَرِيمِ – *What has deluded you concerning your Generous Lord?* Here, he argues, the "bi-" (بِ) is likewise used in the sense of "an" (عَنْ). He explains the verse as: أَي مَا خَدَعَكَ عَنِ رَبِّكَ الْكَرِيمِ وَ – *أي ما خدعك عن ربك الكريم* – *meaning: what deceived you away from (belief in) your Generous Lord*.

Providing detailed information about the preposition ‘alā (عَلَى), Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūṭī explains that this preposition carries a wide range of meanings and, in certain contexts, may function with the meaning of other prepositions. The prominent 15th-century philologist notes that ‘alā can also be used in the sense of fī (فِي). As an example, he cites verse 15 of Sūrat al-Qaṣaṣ أَهْلُهَا غَفْلَةٌ – *He entered the city at a time when its people were unaware*. The philologist explains that in this verse, the phrase ‘alā ḥīnin (عَلَى حِينَ) should be understood as fī ḥīnin (فِي حِينَ) – i.e. at the time. He further supports his interpretation with additional

examples.

(al-Suyūfī, 1979, pp. 185–186).

Discussing the preposition ‘alā (على) in detail, Ibn Manzūr also notes that it can be used in the sense of fī (في). To support this claim, he cites the following line of poetry as evidence:

وَلَقَدْ سَرَيْتُ عَلَى الظَّلَامِ بِمِغْشَمٍ جَلِدٍ مِنَ الْفَتَيَانِ غَيْرِ مُهَيَّبِلٍ

(Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 9, p. 380).

Translation: In the darkness of night, I set out with a young man of firm heart, courageous (miğsham – one who plunges into matters without hesitation), and of pleasant character (ğayru muğabbalin – that is, not burdensome in manner). According to Ibn Manzūr, in this shāhid bayt, the usage of ‘alā conveys the sense of fī, indicating a temporal or situational setting – i.e., in the midst of the night’s darkness.

Al-Baghdādī, on the other hand, interprets the word miğsham (مغشم) in the cited verse as being derived from ġašm (غشم) – meaning *oppression* or *injustice*. Under this interpretation, the word does not denote *one who boldly plunges into everything*, but rather is understood as *a tyrant* or *one who commits injustice* (‘Abd al-Qādir al-Baghdādī, 2000, Vol. 8, p. 198). In this verse, the significant linguistic observation is the usage of the preposition ‘alā (على) in the sense of fī (في) – that is, it conveys the meaning *in* rather than *on*, pointing to a temporal or contextual function.

With regard to the usage of prepositions, there were notable differences of opinion between the philological schools of Basra and Kufa. For instance, according to the Kufan scholars, the preposition "min" (من) – which generally conveys the meaning of "*from*" – can be used with nouns denoting both time and place. According to the Basran scholars, however, the preposition min (من) cannot be used with nouns denoting time; rather, it governs only nouns with spatial (locative) meaning in the genitive case. To support their position, the Kufan scholars cite Sūrat al-Tawbah, verse 108: لِمَسْجِدٍ أُسِّسَ عَلَى التَّقْوَى مِنْ أَوَّلِ يَوْمٍ أَحَقُّ أَنْ تَقُومَ فِيهِ - *The mosque founded on righteousness from the first day is more worthy that you stand in it*; and Sūrat al-Jumu‘ah, verse 9: إِذَا نُودِيَ لِلصَّلَاةِ مِنْ يَوْمِ الْجُمُعَةِ - *When the call is proclaimed to prayer on the day of Friday, hasten to the remembrance of Allah*. They argue that in both of these verses, the words governed by the preposition min carry temporal meanings, thus demonstrating that min can indeed govern nouns with the meaning of time. According to the Basran scholars, the preposition min (من) functions analogously to mud (مد), which conveys the meaning of "*since*" or "*from*" in a temporal context. The distinction, as they see it, lies in the fact that min denotes a spatial point of origin, whereas mud denotes a temporal point of origin. In other words, the

Basrans argue that it is incorrect to say: ما رأيته من يوم السبت - *I have not seen him since Saturday*, as this applies a spatial preposition to a temporal noun. Instead, they maintain that the proper construction is: ما رأيته مذ يوم السبت - *I have not seen him since Saturday*, where *mud* appropriately conveys the intended temporal meaning. The Basran grammarians argue that, in the first verse cited by the Kufans, the *min* (من) is in fact elliptical, and that the first term of a genitive construction (*idāfa*) is implied. According to them, the verse should be understood as: من تأسيس أول يوم - *from the founding of the first day*. As for the second verse, they interpret the preposition *min* as being used in the sense of *fī* (في), i.e. the verse effectively means في يوم الجمعة - *on the day of Friday*. It is worth noting, however, that not all Basran scholars strictly adhered to this position. Some prominent philologists from the Basran school, such as al-Mubarrad, Ibn Durustawayh, and others, supported the Kufan view (Abū al-Barakāt al-Anbārī, 2002, pp. 315-318)

The following verse cited by Ibn Manẓūr also aligns with the position of the Kufan grammarians.

لَمَنْ الدِّيارُ بِقُنَّةِ الحِجرِ أَقْوِينَ مِنْ جِجَجٍ وَ مِنْ دَهْرٍ؟

(Ibn Manẓūr, 1988, vol. 3, p. 60).

Translation: "Whom do the houses atop the summit of Hijr belong to those that, with the passing of years and eras, have been abandoned and turned into desolate ruins?"

The particle “min” in this context is used with a noun denoting time, thereby conveying a temporal meaning – specifically, indicating the sense of “since” or “from the time of”. The verse belongs to Zuhayr ibn Abī Sulmā (d. 609 CE), who was regarded as one of the three preeminent poets (aḥad al-thalātha al-muqaddamīn ‘alā sā’ir al-shu‘arā’) of pre-Islamic Arabic poetry. He was referred to as al-ḥakīm –the wise one – among Arab poets of the Jāhiliyyah period and held in higher esteem than many of his contemporaries (Abū al-Faraj al-Iṣfahānī, 2008, p. 226). According to the commentary on his Dīwān, the verse in question is the opening line of a panegyric composed in praise of Ḥarīm ibn Sinān (Abū al-‘Abbās Tha‘lab, 2004, p. 91). Al-Baghdādī notes that Hijr is the name of a location and settlement belonging to the Thamūd tribes, situated in the Wādī al-Qurā region on the way to al-Shām. In contrast, Ḥajr refers to a town located in the al-Yamāmah region in central Arabia. However, the latter is considered unlikely in this context, as the name does not accept the definite article “al”, making such an interpretation less probable (‘Abd al-Qādir al-Baghdādī, 1996).

2. “Fī” Preposition in the shāhid bayts

Ibn Manzūr, who presents insightful views regarding the preposition “fī” as it relates to the meaning conveyed by the suffix – in, on, at, first discusses the verb “fayya” (فَيَّ):

“فَيَّ كَلِمَةٌ مَعْنَاهَا التَّعَجُّبُ. يَقُولُونَ: يَا فَيَّ مَا لِي أَفْعَلُ كَذَا! وَقِيلَ مَعْنَاهُ الْأَسْفُ عَلَى شَيْءٍ يَفُوتُ.. فَي تَأْتِي بِمَعْنَى وَسْطٍ وَ تَأْتِي بِمَعْنَى دَاخِلٍ كَقَوْلِكَ: عَبْدُ اللَّهِ فِي الدَّارِ أَيْ دَاخِلَ الدَّارِ وَ وَسْطَ الدَّارِ وَ تَجِيئِي فِي بِمَعْنَى عَلَى وَ فِي التَّنْزِيلِ لِأَصْلِبِنَكُمْ فِي جَنُوعِ النَّخْلِ الْمَعْنَى عَلَى جَنُوعِ النَّخْلِ” (Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 10, p. 372).

Translation: “Fayya” (فَيَّ) is a word that expresses astonishment. The Arabs say: “*Yā fayya mā lī af‘alu kadhā*” – “What is the matter with me, why am I doing this?” Some scholars also assert that the meaning of this word conveys a sense of regret over something lost. The preposition “fī” denotes meanings such as “within,” “inside,” or “in the midst of.” For instance, in the sentence “*‘Abdullāh is at home,*” the implication is that he is inside the house, in its interior or central space. Additionally, “fī” may also take on the meaning of the preposition “‘alā” (“on” or “upon”). In the Qur’anic verse (Tāhā 20:71), it is stated: “*La-uṣallibannakum fī judhū‘ al-nakhl*” – “I will crucify you in the trunks of palm trees”. This expression is interpreted as: “*La-uṣallibannakum ‘alā judhū‘ al-nakhl*” – “I will crucify you upon the trunks of palm trees”. Thus, “fī” in this context functions in the sense of “‘alā”, denoting location upon rather than within.

Ibn Manzūr illustrates this use of *fī* as *alā* through the couplet:

بَطْلٌ كَانَ ثِيَابَهُ فِي سَرْحَةٍ يُحْدَى نِعَالِ السَّبْتِ لَيْسَ بِتَوَامٍ

(Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 10, p. 372).

Translation: He is a warrior of such stature that it is as if the garment he wears was made not for a man, but for a towering tree – a reference to his tall and upright physique. He wears sandals made of leather tanned with the leaves of the Arab acacia, evoking a sense of ruggedness and native strength. He was not born as a twin, implying that he alone received the full nourishment in the womb – a metaphor for his unmatched strength and completeness of form, as twins are believed to share and thus receive less.

In this context, the expression “fī sarḥatin” illustrates the usage of the preposition “fī” in the sense of “‘alā” (i.e., “on” or “upon”). The word “sarḥah” (سَرْحَةٍ) refers to a tall and large tree, symbolizing grandeur and stature. The term “as-sabt” (السَّبْتِ) denotes leather tanned with the leaves of the qaraz tree (mā dubigha bi-l-qaraz) – that is, with the leaves of the Arabian acacia (*qarāz*). The verse is attributed to ‘Antarah ibn Shaddād, the renowned pre-Islamic poet and author of one of the celebrated Mu‘allaqāt. This particular line is the 60th verse of an 85-verse qaṣīda (Dīwān ‘Antarah, 1970). However, in the commentary by al-Zawzani, the same

qaṣīda comprises only 74 verses (al-Zawzani, 1992). The word “qarāz” (قَرَظٌ) specifically refers to the leaves of the Arab acacia tree, which were traditionally used in the tanning of leather.

Ibn Manzūr, in his extensive discussion of the preposition "fi", demonstrates – based on poetic evidence – that this preposition is also used in the Arabic poetic tradition to convey meanings typically expressed by the suffix “-a⁴” – with”, as well as by the prepositions "ma'a" (indicating accompaniment) and "bi" (indicating means or instrumentality) (Ibn Manzūr, vol. 10, 1988).

3. “Ila” and “Fi” Prepositions in shāhid bayts

A number of grammarians have pointed out that the preposition "ilā", which typically indicates direction and corresponds to the suffix “-a⁴” in Azerbaijani, can, in certain contexts, also function with the meaning of "fi" (i.e., “in” or “within”). Among these scholars is Ibn Mālik, who advances this view in his work *Sharḥ al-Tashīl* (Ibn Mālik, 1990, p. 143). According to Ibn Mālik, the preposition "ilā" in Qur'anic verses such as *al-Nisā'* 4:87 and *al-An'ām* 6:12 – specifically in the phrase "*la-yajma'annakum ilā yawm al-qiyāmah*" (*He will surely gather you until/on the Day of Resurrection*) – should be understood as carrying the meaning of "fi" ("in" or "on"). Ibn Manzūr also comments on this phenomenon when discussing the semantic range of "ilā", he likewise refers to poetic evidence, demonstrating that in some instances, "ilā" indeed functions with the meaning of "fi".

فَلَا تَتْرُكْنِي بِالْوَعِيدِ كَأَنِّي إِلَى النَّاسِ مَطْلِيٍّ بِهِ الْفَارُ أَجْرَبُ

(Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 1, p. 196).

Translation: "Do not cast me among people, threatened and shunned, like a mangy camel coated in tar".

This verse serves as evidence for the usage of "ilā" with the meaning of "fi" – as seen in the phrase "*ka'annanī fi al-nās*" (as if I were among the people). The line belongs to al-Nābiḡah al-Dhubyānī (Dīwān al-Nābiḡah al-Dhubyānī, 1991, p. 24). In this qaṣīda, the poet addresses al-Nu'mān ibn al-Mundhir, the king of the Lakhmids, praising him and pleading for forgiveness. Al-Nābiḡah had previously fled from al-Nu'mān due to certain accusations and sought refuge with the Ghassānid rulers in Syria, in whose praise he composed panegyrics. Naturally, this incurred the displeasure of al-Nu'mān. Later, feeling remorseful, al-Nābiḡah sought forgiveness from al-Nu'mān in several of his qaṣīdas, including the one from which the aforementioned verse is cited. In these poems, he expresses regret for having aligned himself with the Banū Jafna, i.e., the Ghassānid rulers, and emphasizes that the accusations made against him were unfounded. In the cited verse, al-Nābiḡah once again turns to al-Nu'mān,

pleading with him not to threaten or punish him. A camel afflicted with mange would be smeared with tar (zift) and kept away from the rest of the herd to prevent contagion. Al-Nābiḡah, likening himself to such a camel, alludes to the fact that, due to the king's threat and disapproval, people began to avoid him, distancing him from their gatherings and excluding him from their social circles. In this qaṣīda, the poet later elevates al-Nu'mān by metaphorically comparing him to the sun, while referring to other kings merely as stars – thus emphasizing al-Nu'mān's singular status and radiant superiority over all others.

فإنك شمس والملوك كواكب
إذا طلعت لم يبدُ منهن كوكبٌ

(Dīwān al-Nābiḡah al-Dhubayānī, 1991, p. 25).

Translation: you are a sun, while kings are but stars; when the sun rises, no star remains visible.

Al-Baghdādī explains that al-wa'id (الوعيد) means "threat", while al-qār (الغار) refers to "tar." In fact, the phrase in question is: "maṭlīyyun bi-l-qār" – *smeared with tar*" ('Abd al-Qādir al-Baghdādī, 1996, vol. 9, pp. 465–466). However, Ibn 'Uṣfūr, in his work "Ḍarā'ir al-Shi'r", interprets the word maṭlīyyun (مَطْلِيٌّ) in this verse not literally, but figuratively. According to him, it conveys the meaning of "mubaḡḡad" or "mubḡaḡ" – that is, "despised," "hated," or "repulsive" (Ibn 'Uṣfūr, 1980, p. 238).

In his discussion of the meanings of the preposition "ilā", Ibn Manzūr cites the interpretations of Ibn al-'Abbās and several other grammarians regarding its usage in Sūrat al-Mā'idah, verse 6: "fa-ghsilū wujūhakum wa aydiyakum ilā al-marāfiq" ("...wash your faces and your hands up to the elbows"). He notes that the preposition "ilā" in this context is understood to carry the meaning of "ma'a" (with), which in turn corresponds to the function of the suffix "-la" in Azerbaijani – indicating inclusion, not mere limit. Ibn Manzūr further argues – based on poetic evidence – that one of the extended meanings of "ilā" is also "inda" (at, by, in the presence of).

نَقَالَ، إِذَا زَادَ النِّسَاءُ: حَرِيدَةٌ
صَنَاعٌ، فَقَدْ سَادَتْ إِلَيَّ الْعَوَانِيَا

(Ibn Manzūr, 1988, vol. 1, p. 197).

Translation: While other women move from one tent to another, engaging in social visits, the mother of Wabr remains within her home, silent and reserved. She is untouched – pure, skilled, and, in my eyes, surpasses all other beauties.

In this instance, the word "ilayya" is used with the meaning of "'indī" (*with me, in my presence*), that is, the preposition "ilā" conveys the sense of "inda" (*at or with*). The verse is attributed to 'Ubayd ibn Ḥusayn al-Namirī, known by his epithet "al-Rā'ī" (*the Shepherd*), who

died in 709 CE (Dīwān al-Rā'ī al-Namirī, 1995, p. 243). In the *Lisān al-'Arab*, this line is recorded with a variant reading in the first word: "yuqāl" instead of "thiqāl", reflecting a transmission difference. However, the version found in the poet's Dīwān is considered more accurate – particularly in terms of semantic clarity – and is therefore preferred. The word "thiqāl" (ثِقَالٌ) is interpreted to mean: “al-mar'ah al-mulāzimah li-makānihā” – *a woman who remains in her place*, that is, one who stays confined to her home or abode.

4. Preposition “Ḥattā” in shāhid bayts

Discussing ḥattā, Ibn Manẓūr quotes al-Jawharī:

"وقال الجوهري: حتى فعلى وهي حرف تكون جارة بمنزلة الى في الانتهاء والغاية وتكون عاطفة بمنزلة الواو وقد تكون حرف ابتداء يستأنف بها الكلام بعدها كما قال جرير يهجو الأخطل ويذكر إيقاع الجحاف بقومه:
فَمَا زَالَتْ أَلْتَلَى تَمُجُّ دِمَاءُهَا بَدَجَلَةٌ حَتَّى مَاءٍ دَجَلَةٌ أَشْكَلُ
لَنَا الْفَضْلُ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَأَنْفُكَ رَاغِمٌ وَنَحْنُ لَكُمْ يَوْمَ الْقِيَامَةِ أَفْضَلُ

(Ibn Manẓūr, 1988, vol. 3, p. 39).

Al-Jawharī stated that the word "ḥattā" follows the morphological pattern of fa'la. It functions similarly to "ilā" in that it conveys the meaning of termination (*intiha*) and governs a noun in the genitive case. Additionally, it can serve the role of a coordinating conjunction, like "wāw", and at times functions as a particle of initiation (*ḥarf ibtidā'*), meaning it can occur at the beginning of a sentence. This can be observed in a poem by Jarīr, in which he criticizes al-Akhtal and recalls how he caused destruction and bloodshed upon his tribe. The usage of "ḥattā" at the start of the line supports this grammatical analysis.

The meaning of the bayts: "The blood of the slain still clouds the waters of the Tigris, staining its current with red. The river, though white, flows tinged with crimson. Even if it displeases you, virtue, honor, and nobility belong to us in this world, and on the Day of Judgment, we shall remain superior to you".

In this instance, "ḥattā" is not functioning as a preposition governing a noun in the genitive case, but rather as a particle of initiation (*ḥarf ibtidā'*). This is evident in the verse, where the word following "ḥattā" – "al-mā'" (*the water*) – appears in the nominative case (*marfū'*), not in the genitive (*majrūr*), as would be expected if "ḥattā" were functioning as a preposition.

The verse can be found both in Jarīr's Dīwān (Dīwān Jarīr, 1986: 367) and in a commentary written on the Dīwān ('Abdullāh al-Ṣāwī, undated: 457). However, the sequence of the verses in the poet's Dīwān and its commentary does not correspond to the order presented by Ibn Manẓūr. Between these verses, there is an additional verse that appears in the Dīwān but is not included in Ibn Manẓūr's arrangement.

One of the syntactic features of the preposition "ḥattā" is that when it governs a verb, it does so through the implied particle "'an", thereby placing the verb in the subjunctive mood (*manṣūb*). For example: "Sirtu ilā al-Kūfah ḥattā adkhulahā" – *I traveled to Kufa in order to enter it*. Among the Hudhayl tribe, the word "ḥattā" is pronounced with the 'ayn letter, as "'attā", reflecting a dialectal variation (Ibn Manẓūr, 1988, vol. 3, p. 40). As an example of "ḥattā" functioning as a coordinating conjunction, consider the sentence: "Jā'anī al-ṭullāb ḥattā Khālidun" – *The students came to me, even Khālid*. Here, "ḥattā" joins Khālid to the preceding noun phrase "al-ṭullāb" (the students), functioning as a connector that includes an additional element in the coordination.

Conclusion

It should be noted that classical (medieval) philologists based virtually all of their grammatical theories and observations on Arabic poetry. It is precisely through examples and citations drawn from Arabic verse – referred to as “shāhid bayts” (proof) – that specific grammatical rules were established and demonstrated. In addition to poetry, grammatical principles were also explained by reference to verses from the Qur'an, which, naturally, served as a powerful confirmation of the scientific validity, accuracy, and undeniable authority of such rules. To use the terminology of the medieval period, the “literary sciences” (*‘ulūm al-adab*) were understood as a group of disciplines whose main purpose was to interpret and render intelligible the Arabic word – especially in its eloquent and artistic forms. These disciplines numbered more than ten in total and, from a modern perspective, may rightly be considered as branches of what we now call philology.

References

- ‘Abd al-Qadir ibn ‘Umar al-Baghdadi. (1996). *Khizanat al-adab wa lub lubab Lisan al-‘Arab* (C. 9). Maktabat al-Khanji. (In Arabic).
- ‘Abd al-Qadir ibn ‘Umar al-Baghdadi. (2000). *Khizanat al-adab wa lub lubab Lisan al-‘Arab* (C. 8). Maktabat al-Khanji. (In Arabic).
- Abu al-‘Abbas Tha‘lab. (2004). *Sharḥ Diwan Zuhayr ibn Abi Sulma*. Dar al-Kitab al-‘Arabi.
- Abu al-Barakat al-Anbari. (1957). *Asrar al-‘Arabiyya*. Matba‘at al-Zaki. (In Arabic).
- Abu al-Barakat al-Anbari. (2002). *Al-Insaf fi masa’il al-khilaf bayn al-Basriyyin wa al-Kufiyyin*. Maktabat al-Khanji. (In Arabic).
- Abu al-Faraj al-Isfahani. (2008). *Kitab al-Aghani* (C.10). Dar Sadir. (In Arabic).
- Ahmad Saqr. (1935). *Sharḥ Diwan ‘Alqama al-Fahl*. al-Matba‘a al-Mahmudiyya. (In Arabic).

Al-Zawzani. (1992). *Sharḥ al-Mu‘allaqat al-Sab‘*. Lajnat al-Tahqiq fi al-Dar al-‘Alamiyya. (In Arabic).

Diwan al-Nabigha al-Dhubyani. (1991). Sharḥ wa-ta‘liq: Dr. Hanna Nasr al-Hatti. Dar al-Kitab al-‘Arabi. (In Arabic).

Diwan al-Qaṭami. (2001). Mu‘allif: ‘Umair ibn Shuyaym al-Taghlibi. Dr. Mahmud al-Rubay‘i. al-Hay‘a al-Masriyya al-‘Amma lil-Kutub. (In Arabic).

Diwan al-Ra‘i al-Numeiri. (1995). Wadih al-Samad. Dar al-Jil. (In Arabic).

Diwan ‘Antara. (1970). Tahqiq wa-dirasa: Muhammad Said Mulawi. al-Maktab al-Islami. (In Arabic).

Diwan Imru’ al-Qays. (1984). Tahqiq: Muhammad Abu al-Faḍl Ibrahim. Dar al-Ma‘arif. (In Arabic).

Diwan Jarir. (1986). Dar Beirut li-l-Tiba‘a wa-l-Nashr. (In Arabic).

Ibn ‘Asfur al-Ishbili. (1980). *Darā’ir al-shi‘r* (Tahqiq: al-Sayyid Ibrahim Muhammad). Dar al-Andalus. (In Arabic).

Ibn Malik al-Andalusi. (1990). *Sharḥ al-tashil* (C. 3). al-Ji Hajr li-l-Tiba‘a wa-l-Tawzi‘. (In Arabic).

Ibn Manzur. (1988). *Lisan al-‘Arab* (C.1). Dar Ihya’ al-Turath al-‘Arabi. (In Arabic).

Ibn Manzur. (1988). *Lisan al-‘Arab* (C.10). Dar Ihya’ al-Turath al-‘Arabi. (In Arabic).

Ibn Manzur. (1988). *Lisan al-‘Arab* (C.3). Dar Ihya’ al-Turath al-‘Arabi. (In Arabic).

Ibn Manzur. (1988). *Lisan al-‘Arab* (C.9). Dar Ihya’ al-Turath al-‘Arabi. (In Arabic).

Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti. (1979). *Hama‘ al-Hawami‘ fi sharḥ Jam‘ al-Jawami‘* (C.4). Dar al-Buhuth al-‘Ilmiyya. (In Arabic).

Muhammad Isma‘il ‘Abd Allah al-Sawi. (n.d.). *Sharḥ Diwan Jarir*. Matba‘at al-Sawi. (In Arabic).